

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt with Benzyltriethylammonium Chloride

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Manuscript received 1 July 1985, revised 29 April 1987, accepted 5 June 1987

A simple and rapid extractive spectrophotometric method for the determination of cobalt(II) is described. The ion-association formed between the SCN^- -complex of Co^{2+} and benzyltriethylammonium ion is extracted into 1,2-dichloroethane in a wide range of pH. The extracted species has an absorption maximum at 625 nm, and obeys Beer's law for 0.5–55 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Co^{2+} ; the molar absorptivity being $0.179 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Optimum conditions for colour development and interference from foreign ions have been studied.

A number of quaternary ammonium salts find application as reagent in the determination of metal ions in microquantities. Preparation and some reactions of benzyltriethylammonium chloride have been reported¹⁻³. Its use in the spectrophotometric determination of metals has, however, not been found reported.

The present work describes a method for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) in SCN^- solutions using benzyltriethylammonium chloride as reagent and 1,2-dichloroethane as the extracting solvent. Although the thiocyanate method for the determination of cobalt is well known, it suffers from the disadvantage of low sensitivity (0.055 $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$) and a large number of foreign ions interfere in the determination. In the present method, the sensitivity is considerably improved (0.03 $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$) and interference due to foreign ions is minimised. This method is conspicuous by virtue of its high degree of precision, accuracy and selectivity.

Experimental

A Beckman DK-2 spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path was used for absorbance measurements, and pH values were determined with a Elico LI-10 pH meter.

All chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade. Cobalt(II) chloride (A.R.) was dissolved in distilled water to prepare a standard solution containing 50×10^{-4} g of Co per ml.

Benzyltriethylammonium chloride: A mixture of ethyl acetate, dimethylformamide, triethylamine and benzyl chloride in the molar ratio 1 : 2 : 2 : 2, respectively, was refluxed for 1 h. Sufficient benzene was then added at 80° and the precipitate after washing repeatedly with benzene was dried in vacuum⁴.

A 0.05 M solution of benzyltriethylammonium chloride and a 30% solution of potassium thiocyanate were prepared in distilled water.

Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their chloride, nitrate or sulphate; or from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts. Solutions of 0.2 M Na_2HPO_4 and 0.1 M citric acid were prepared to constitute the buffer recommended for the determination.

Procedure :

An aliquot of the cobalt solution containing 2.5–275 μg of Co^{2+} was made upto 3 ml with water and citric acid- Na_2HPO_4 buffer such that the pH of the medium was maintained at 4. To it 30% potassium thiocyanate solution (1 ml), 0.05 M benzyltriethylammonium chloride solution (1 ml) and 1,2-dichloroethane solution (5 ml) were added. The resulting mixture was shaken for 1 min and the blue organic layer separated. Absorbance of the extract was measured at 625 nm against the pure solvent. Amounts of cobalt in unknown solutions were calculated from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The reagent, benzyltriethylammonium chloride (QCl) reacts with the SCN^- -complex of cobalt(II) yielding the ion-pair $(\text{Q}^+)_2(\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4)^{2-}$ in the form of a blue precipitate which is completely extractable into 1,2-dichloroethane. The extract shows an absorption maximum at 625 nm, and obeys Beer's law over the concentrations range 0.5–55 ppm of Co^{2+} . Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are found to be $0.197 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.03 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The colour of the complex was found to remain stable for more than 24 h.

The pure solvent could be used as the reference for a wide range of pH (2-8) in citric acid - Na₂HPO₄ buffer medium. The same values of the absorbance were also obtained by performing the extraction from a sulphuric acid solution with concentrations upto 0.5 N with respect to the acid. Here too, the reagent blank was devoid of any absorption at 625 nm. When the sulphuric acid concentration was made to exceed 0.5 N, measurement of the absorbance needed the reagent blank as the reference solution. Acidity of the aqueous layer, however, had to be maintained below 3 N, since further acidity produced low values of absorbance.

Effect of the thiocyanate concentration on absorbance was studied by using thiocyanate solutions of varying concentrations, e.g. from 1 to 50%. It was found that concentrations below 1% in the aqueous layer resulted in low absorbance while increased concentrations were without any significant effect.

As regards reagent concentrations, 1 ml of 0.05 M solution of benzyltriethylammonium chloride was adequate for complete extraction of the complex for the concentration range of cobalt (2.5-275 µg) determined. Reagent concentrations below 0.002 M in the aqueous layer produced low values while a concentration upto 0.2 M was devoid of any change in the absorbance.

Effect of foreign ions : A number of representative ions were examined to study their interference

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON EXTRACTION OF COBALT

Cobalt taken = 50 µg			
Ions added	Tolerance limit (mg)	Ions added	Tolerance limit (mg)
Cu ^{II}	0.025	Mn ^{II}	10
Ag ^I	10	Mn ^{VII}	1.2
Au ^{III}	2	Fe ^{II}	0.25
Zn ^{II}	1	Fe ^{III}	0.015
Cd ^{II}	5	Ni ^{II}	10
Hg ^{II}	10	Ru ^{III}	0.06
Sn ^{II}	10	Rh ^{III}	0.5
Sn ^{IV}	1	Pd ^{II}	0.35
Pb ^{II}	10	Pt ^{IV}	1
As ^{III}	10	Fluoride	10
As ^V	10	Bromide	10
Sb ^{III}	10	Iodide	10
Bi ^{III}	0.6	Thiosulphate	10
V ^V	10	Oxalate	10
Cr ^{III}	2	Tartrate	10
Cr ^{VI}	4	Cyanide	0.5
Mo ^{VI}	10	EDTA	0.05
W ^{VI}	10	Thiourea	10

in the determination of cobalt by the recommended procedure. The tolerance limit (Table 1) was set at the amount required to cause less than 3% error. The upper limit of the foreign ion concentration was, however, restricted to 200-fold excess (w/w) of the cobalt concentration.

Interfering effect of iron(III) and copper(II) when present in concentration above the tolerance limit was obviated by making use of potassium fluoride and thiourea, respectively, as masking agents. Tolerance limit could, thus, be raised in both the cases beyond 200-fold excess of cobalt concentration.

Thus the present method proves to be very rapid and simple, and provides an excellent recovery of cobalt in presence of most of the common ions. Added merit of the method is its high degree of precision and accuracy as evident from the standard deviation (0.0029) and coefficient of variation (0.85%) in the absorbance for 10 ppm of cobalt. It is selective in the sense that interference from foreign ions is minimum. This method was found quite suitable for determination of cobalt in ores and synthetic mixtures containing diverse ions (Table 2).

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Composition of mixture and amount taken (µg)	Percentage recovery of cobalt
Co ^{II} (50), Ni ^{II} (250), Fe ^{III} (250)*	99.7
Co ^{II} (50), Mo ^{VI} (250), W ^{VI} (300)	98.2
Co ^{II} (50), V ^V (250), Mn ^{VII} (500)	97.2
Co ^{II} (50), Rh ^{III} (500), Pd ^{II} (250)	99.7

*Extraction was done after adding KF.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. (Mrs.) A. Chaudhuri, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Gauhati University, for facility, and U.G.C., New Delhi, for awarding Teacher Fellowship to one of them (K.B.).

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